

**ECONOMICS OF FLUTED PUMPKIN PRODUCTION AMONG
SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN NEIGHBORHOOD COMMUNITIES OF
NATIONAL HORTICULTURAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE, MBATO
OUTSTATION, OKIGWE, IMO STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract. *The study analyzed the economics of fluted pumpkin production among smallholder farmers in neighborhood communities of National Horticultural Research Institute, Mbato Outstation, Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria. Data were collected with the aid of a well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule using purposive and random sampling techniques. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Result showed that the smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in the area had mean age of 39 years and majority (61.7%) were female who were mostly (76.7%) married with household size of 5 persons.*

Majority (51.7%) had secondary education with mean farming experience of 5 years and mean farm size of 0.5417 hectare. Majority (66.7%) were none members of cooperative society and greater percentages (71.7%) have never had extension contact but their mean annual farm income was ₦73,550. Result further revealed that, the total costs and total revenues of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in wet and dry season production in the study area were ₦148,875 and ₦280,005; ₦155,005 and ₦338,340 respectively. Net return of ₦131,130 and ₦183,335 for wet and dry season production respectively. Benefit to cost ratios were 1.88 and 2.18 respectively and returns on investment were 0.88 and 1.18, with shepherd future of 53.2% and 45.8% for wet and dry season production of fluted pumpkin respectively. The sources of water for dry season production analyzed, showed that majority (55%) of the farmers use perennial stream, and wastewater (26.7%). Other sources according to the farmers' responses were bore-hole (8.3%), dug-outs (5%), pond (3.3%) and rivers (1.7%). Results also, revealed the constraints to profitable fluted pumpkin production in the area. These constraints were categorized into production, economic and managerial. The factors that were classified as production constraints were inadequate improved varieties of seeds (0.518), pests and diseases (0.455), poor feeder roads (0.581) and poor implementation of government policies (0.4375). Also the economic constraints were high cost of inputs (0.526), instability of product prices (0.4655), high cost of transportation (0.4635) and inadequate credit facilities (0.5331). Furthermore, the managerial constraints were inadequate extension contact (0.5885), nature of land ownership (0.526), poor market information (0.563), Lack of irrigation facilities (0.518), poor storage facilities (0.4065) and lack of processing facilities (0.5162). However, the study concluded that fluted pumpkin production in wet and dry seasons were profitable and recommended that the farmers should join

cooperatives, have regular extension contacts and attend seminars and workshops that could improve their production and management skills. Government and non-governmental organizations should intervene in the area of basic amenities such as good road, electricity and water supply as people in the area have never enjoyed electricity in their life, hence the high level of deterioration, perishability and postharvest losses of produce experienced by the farmers as there are no reasonable storage and processing facilities for shelf life extension of their produce.

Keywords: *Fluted pumpkin, Smallholder, Neighborhood, Mbato, Okigwe*

Introduction. *Telfairia occidentalis* (fluted pumpkin) “Ugu” is a member of the Cucurbitaceae and a popular vegetable widely grown and consumed in Nigeria and across the tropics (Nwanguma and Akinpelu, 2020). It is widely cultivated all year round, in Southern Nigeria as a leaf and seed vegetable. Rain-fed crop production is between March and November while the dry season irrigated crop is between November and March. *Telfairia* is propagated by seeds and in some cases, vegetative. It thrives better in well-drained soils but it is not shade-loving. *Telfairia* is an important crop grown for its leaves and edible seeds. It is highly acceptable among the Nigerian populace and it brings better returns compared to other common tropical leafy vegetables (Layade, Adeoye, Ngbede and Utobo 2020). According to them, leaves and seeds of *Telfairia* are of high nutritional, medicinal and industrial values, being rich in protein, fat and vitamins and therefore calls for regular consumption. The seeds are used as propagating materials, eaten roasted, boiled or blended to paste as soup thickener. The cultivation/production of *Telfairia* has increased rapidly as a result of its economic values in terms of monetary return to the growers especially during dry season farming. *Telfairia*

production can provide all year round income generating employment opportunities for the farmers with little capital investment (Layade, *et al.*, 2020). Fluted pumpkin consumption has increased over the years and it is an important component of the daily diets of Nigerians (Okoli and Mgbeogu, 1983). Due to its hypolipidemic action, it lowers blood cholesterol and thus protects from a large range of associated complications like cardiac problems, hypertension and diabetes (Margret, 2011). The joint FAO/WHO (2003) consultation on diet, nutrition and prevention of chronic disease recommended a minimum intake of 400g of leafy vegetables which helps in preventing and managing of nutritional and also health related diseases that are rampant in rural areas. According to WHO (2003), the nutritional contribution of fluted pumpkin is essential for good health and growth among lactating mothers. The seed of fluted pumpkin contains essential nutrients in significant amounts which can supplement other foods (Christian, 2007). According to him, adding fluted pumpkin seeds to diet compares favorably with conventional drugs in reducing inflammatory symptoms of arthritis.

Farmers strive to maximize yield of high quality using effective chemical substances on the crop grown. Nitrogen is essential for adequate vegetation and should ideally be given in the form of manure, applied before planting. The use of well-decomposed manure is essential for fruit production and in this case it is recommended that about one kilogram of manure/ plant be applied. Fluted pumpkin is perennial when grown on well-drained soils, slightly shaded and mulched but not so soggy soils (Idowu, Alimi, Tijani and Okobi, 2007). In the study area, the crop is grown on poor soils as an annual during the rainy season and also during the dry season adopting manual irrigation practices. Majorly, it is grown along-side other crops such as yam, maize, cassava e.t.c. as against Olowa and Olowa (2016) who maintained that fluted pumpkin is not majorly grown

along-side other crops as done in other climes. Fluted pumpkin is very important in the diet of children, men, women, nursing mothers as well as livestock due to its high nutritive value. But in Nigeria, the output has not been able to meet the demand for human food not to mention that of livestock feed. As a result of the growing need, the task of producing enough fluted pumpkin poses an increasing challenge. Like other crops, it is affected by the seasonality syndrome, hence, the irrigation practices in dry season. The question is whether there is difference in profitability of dry season/ irrigated and rain-fed practices so far in lieu of excessive dry season or inequitable distribution of rainfall attributed to climate change, hence the need to analyze the economics of fluted pumpkin production in the neighborhood communities of National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Mbato Outstation, Okigwe, Imo State.

However, several studies in Nigeria have been carried out to analyze profitability of crops and more specifically vegetables. Udoh and Akpan, (2007) in their study estimated the profitability of vegetable farmers in Akwa Ibom State and reported that farmers made profit of \$1765.53 per hectare. Ala (2013) examined profitability of yam production by women in Bosso Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria using farm budgeting. The result showed that farmers obtained a net profit of \$63.39/ha. Similarly, Nwauwa and Omonona (2010) in their study on fluted pumpkin production under irrigation system in Ilorin found fertilizer, labour, and plot size as significant factors. More specifically, Ayinde, Akerele, and Ojeniyi (2007); Idowu, Alimi, Tijani and Okobi (2007) examined economic factors affecting the production of fluted pumpkin using a modified cost-route approach and reported fluted pumpkin production as being profitable under existing production systems with an average net income of \$205.90/ha on a mean farm size of 0.301. Ayoola (2014) assessed the profitability of vegetable farming under

irrigation and rain-fed systems using the gross margin, net profit, benefit-cost, shepherd-future and regression approach and concluded that investment on irrigation for vegetable production would be worthwhile for growing commercial vegetable enterprise in the study area. Regarding constraints faced by fluted pumpkin farmers, Nwosu, Onyeneke and Okoli, (2012) reported lack of credit facilities, lack of availability of inputs, pests and disease infestation, inadequate information about input and output prices, and poor road network respectively. Olowa and Olowa (2016) assessed the profitability of growing fluted pumpkin on commercial scale in Ikorodu Local Government Area (ILGA) using frequency distribution, percentages, means, gross margin, net profit, benefit-cost and Shepherd-Future analyses, and exponential regression model of combined profit function for irrigation and rain-fed systems. Results showed that fluted pumpkin farming was equally undertaken by both male and female mostly between 41-50 years old, with no formal education and average family size of 6 per household, net profit of ₦380,150 and ₦207,150 and benefit-cost ratios of 2.7 and 3 for rain-fed and dry season/irrigated practice respectively. According to them, farm size and level of education have positive correlation while age and costs of fertilizer, labour and planting materials were negatively related to farmer's profit at 1% and 5% significant level and maintained that, farmers should not invest in irrigation for fluted pumpkin production and that, increased access to land, fertilizers and improved seeds would promote profitability and commercialization of fluted pumpkin enterprises in Nigeria.

Akanni-John, Shaib-Rahim, Eniola, and Elesho (2020) analyze the economics of fluted pumpkin production in Ibadan metropolis using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, profit function analysis, gross margin and fluted pumpkin production was found to be a profitable venture in the study area.

Ogisi, Chukwuji and Okeke (2014) examined profitability of fluted pumpkin (*Telfaria occidentalis* Hook F. Cucurbitaceae) production in Ukwuani local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics. According to them, Farmers operated on subsistence level, about 95% practiced mixed cropping with farming experience not less than 5 years. Net return per hectare was \$644.90 and benefit-cost ratio was \$1 to \$1.23 which implied that for every \$1 invested, 23cents was obtained thus depicted that, the enterprise was profitable in the study area. Utobo and Nwankwo (2019) analyzed inputs-output relationship of fluted pumpkin farmers in Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria, using four functional forms of multiple regression analysis. Result showed that sixty-nine percent (69%) of the variations in the quantity of fluted pumpkin produced by farmers in the study area were accounted for, by the explanatory variables. Household size (0.203), farming experiences (0.106), man-days of labour (0.495), fertilizer (0.110), capital resources (0.642) were statistically and positively significant at 1%. Education level (0.272) Cost of seed (0.066) were also positively related to fluted pumpkin output at 5% level of significance. Contrarily, Farm size (-0.011), Extension contact (-0.113) and Cost of agrochemical (-0.014) were negatively related to fluted pumpkin output at 5% level of significance. Annual farm income was negatively related to fluted pumpkin output at 10% level of significance. The elasticity of production (return to scale) was (1.806) which implied increasing return to scale for fluted pumpkin farmers in the study area. Utobo, Ngbede, Nwanguma and Nwankwo, (2017) estimated profitability and resource-use efficiency of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in Ebonyi state, Nigeria using efficiency ratio, costs and returns analysis. Results showed efficiency ratios (MVP/MFC) of land (0.01496), labour (0.1148), seed (0.12806), fertilizer (0.0042), and agrochemical (0.0039) respectively as being < 1 , meaning over-

utilization of these resources and maintained that fluted pumpkin production in the study area was profitable. All these findings were in consonance with Adebisi-Adelani, Olajide-Taiwo, Adeoye, Olajide-Taiwo (2011) who maintained that fluted pumpkin is the most important and extensively cultivated food and income generating crops in many parts of Africa.

Objectives of the study

The broad objective of the study is to analyze the economics of fluted pumpkin production in the neighborhood communities of National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Mbato Outstation, Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to;

- 1) describe the socioeconomic characteristics of fluted pumpkin farmers;
- 2) estimate the relative profitability of rain-fed and dry season fluted pumpkin production;
- 3) identify the sources of water for dry season production of fluted pumpkin;
- 4) analyze the constraints on profitable fluted pumpkin production in the area.

Methodology

Study Area

The study was conducted within the neighborhood communities of National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Mbato Outstation, Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria. The institute is located on latitude $5^{\circ} 31' N$, and longitude $7^{\circ} 23' E$ above 131m above sea level with average rainfall of 2330mm per annum. The institute is surrounded by agrarian communities and farmers there are horticultural crop producers owing to the presence of the national horticultural research institute. They produce mostly fruits and vegetable, sourcing planting materials such as improved seeds and seedlings directly from the institute and out-growers.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Purposive and random Sampling techniques were adopted for this study. There are five (5) communities that surround NIHORT. They include Aku, Agbobu, Umulolo, Umuawa Ibu and Okigwe urban. The study purposively selected three (3) communities that are so close to the institute, namely; Agbobu, Umulolo and Umuawa Ibu. Twenty (20) fluted pumpkin farmers were selected randomly from each of the three (3) communities to give sixty (60) fluted pumpkin farmers for the study

Data collection and Analysis

Primary data for this study were sourced with the aid of well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule in the case of illiterate farmers. Data generated for this study were analyzed using the following tools, namely: descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means and percentages; cost and return analysis such as net return, return on investment, cost-benefit ratio and shepherd future; and principal component factor analysis (PCA). Objectives I and III were achieved using descriptive statistics such as tables, frequencies and percentages. Objective II was achieved using cost and return analysis while objective IV was achieved using principal component factor analysis (PCA).

Model Specification

Costs and Returns Analysis

The costs and returns analysis that was used for this study is expressed thus:

$$NR = TR - TC \quad (1)$$

$$TR = Q \times P \quad (2)$$

$$ROI = NR/TC \quad (3)$$

$$BCR = TR/TC \quad (4)$$

$$SF = (TC/TR) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where,

NR = Net return on fluted pumpkin vines and fruit (Naira)

TR = Total revenue from fluted pumpkin vines and fruits (Naira)

TC = Total Cost of fluted pumpkin production (Naira)

Q = Quantity of fluted pumpkin vines and fruits (Kilogram)

P = Unit price of fluted pumpkin vines and fruits (Naira)

ROI = Return on investment in fluted pumpkin Production (Naira)

SF = Shepherd future(Percentage)

Factor Analysis

The study used the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or factor loading according to child (1973), DeCoster (1998) as adopted by Nwibo and Okorie (2013) to achieve objective III. From them, PCA was predicted on the assumption that:

1) The observable factors, F_j were independent of one another and the error terms, and such that $E(F_j) = 0$ and $Var(F_j) = 1$. Therefore, each observable variable or factor Y_i is a linear function of independent factors, F_i and error terms, et. Quantitatively, factor analysis is linearly represented as:

$$Y_i = \alpha_{i0} + \alpha_{i1}F_1 + \alpha_{i2}F_2 + \alpha_{i3}F_3 + \alpha_{i4}F_4 + \alpha_{i5}F_5 + \alpha_{i6}F_6 \dots + \alpha_{in}F_n + e_i \quad (6)$$

Where:

α_i = Parameters or Loadings. Thus, $\alpha_1 - \alpha_n$ is the coefficient of loading of variable Y_i on factors F_n .

2) The error terms e_i are independent of one another, such that $E(e_i) = 0$ and $Var(e_i) = \delta_i^2$. Thus, each e_i is an outcome is an outcome of a random draw with replacement from a population of e_i values having mean of 0 and certain variance, δ_i^2

From the rule of thumb as developed by Kaiser and adopted by Nwibo and Okorie (2013), variable with a minimum of loading of 0.4 can be isolated as being positive to the attribute in question. Therefore, objective III was subjected to factor analysis.

Results and discussion. The research results/findings in relation to the earlier stated specific objectives of the study were presented thus.

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Smallholder Fluted Pumpkin Farmers in the Area

The socioeconomic attributes were described and presented with their respective frequencies, mean and percentages in table 1.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Smallholder Fluted Pumpkin farmers in the area (n=60)

Socioeconomic Variables	Frequencies	Percentages	Mean
Age of farmer (Years)			38.52
≤30	20	33.3	
31-50	22	36.7	
≥50	18	30	
Sex			
Male	23	38.3	
Female	37	61.7	
Marital status			
Single	13	21.7	
Married	46	76.7	
Widowed	1	1.7	
Household size (person)			5.17
≤5	33	55	
6-10	24	40	
≥11	3	5	
Education level			
Primary	12	20	
Secondary	31	51.7	
Tertiary	17	28.3	

Farming experience (Years)			5.47
≤5	32	53.3	
6-10	23	38.4	
≥11	5	8.3	
Farm size (Hectares)			0.54
0.1-0.5	39	65	
0.6-1.0	10	16.7	
1.1-1.5	11	18.3	
Membership of cooperative			
Member	20	33.3	
Non member	40	66.7	
Frequency of extension contact			
No contact	43	71.7	
Once a week	1	1.7	
Once a month	16	26.7	
Annual farm income (₦)			₦73,550
≤50,000	29	48.3	
51,000-100,000	17	28.4	
101,000-150,000	9	15	
≥151,000	5	8.3	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 indicated that smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in the study area had mean age of 38.52 years, which implied that the farmers were at their active, innovative and productive age. This finding was in consonance with the findings of Onyebinama (2004) who reported that the technical and managerial competence of the farmers would be determined by age, which is likely to influence his attitudes, motivations and behavioural patterns which in turn influences innovation adoption and sensitivity to risk. Innovation adoption would likely increase as age of the farmer increases. In the light of the above the youths need to be considered and encouraged in the implementation of intervention projects in the study area. Majority (61.7%) of the farmers were female and greater percentages (76.7%) of them were married, with mean household size of five (5) persons. These findings agreed with Akpan; Udoh; Bassey; Inya-Agha and Udoh. (2012) who reported

female dominance in waterleaf and fluted pumpkin production in Southern Nigeria which revealed the significance of agricultural activities to the sustenance of women folk especially married ones with sizeable household size as seen in the study area. These results disagreed with Mustapha *et al.* (2016) who reported male dominance in vegetable production in Northern Nigeria with high household size. Majority (51.7%) of the farmers had secondary education with mean farming experience of five (5) and mean farm size of 0.5 hectares. The educational attainment of the farmers showed that, at least, they can read and write and adapt to the technicalities of innovations, product and factor markets and the bureaucratic procedures of farm firm. Five (5) years of farming experience showed that the farmers were still young in the field, though, Onubuogu (2013) observed that years of farming experience would boost the skills of the farmer and a better understanding of the risks associated to farming and the skills for effective resource utilization as well as could predict market condition for higher profitability. The mean farm size of 0.5 hectares showed that farmers were smallholders and any holding less than 3 hectares is small and farmers within the bracket are smallholder farmers (World bank, 2007). This result also agreed with Awoke (2002), Alimba and Ezinwa (2001) whose works reported that most of the farmers in Nigeria were smallholders who cultivated less than 3 hectares annually. And also, in agreement with, FMAWR, 2008, Ogisi et al, (2012) whose works maintained that more than 90% of agricultural output is provided by smallholder farmers with less than two (2) hectares under cultivation. Majority (66.7%) of the farmers did not belong to social organization while (33.3%) of the farmers belong to social organization. This revealed the reasons why farmers complained inadequacy of all necessary production inputs for fluted pumpkin production in the area. Because membership of social organization implied that the farmers could

jointly pool their resources together to enhance efficiency and easily obtain loan, and input grants from the government, and also enables the farmers to exchange ideas, as well as adoption of modern farming techniques and the need to purchase inputs in large quantities so as to enjoy bulk discount. Membership of cooperative society means that the farmers could pool their resources together among others and ease their access to agricultural loan facility to increase and contribute to solving the food security challenge of the country (World Bank, 2007). Majority (71.7%) of the farmers never had extension agents' visit. This revealed the inadequacies of extension agents in the area and this would translate to their inability to identify the weaknesses and strength of the farmers so as to guide them in the adoption and acceptance of new techniques and technologies in fluted pumpkin production. this would also mean a gap between extension agents and farmers, hence, the increase in poverty of the smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in the area. The adverse effect of this is the return of poor productivity on investment and absence of efficiency in input usage (Onumadu; Nwosu and Nwaobiala, 2014). The mean annual farm income of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in the area was ₦73,550. This would mean that the farmers could procure production inputs from open market in the absence of Government subsidy on resource inputs as well as send their wards to school and attain to other needs of the farm family. This mean annual farm income really showed that the farmers were still smallholders who have little or no access to improved/modern facilities/production inputs to boost their output for greater profitability and standard of living. If the farmer has no other sources of income, it implied that the farmer cannot afford three square meal talk more of ensuring quality education/health care for his/her children.

Relative Profitability of Wet and Dry Season Smallholder Fluted Pumpkin Production

The costs and returns analyzed were total variable cost, total fixed cost as well as total revenue from the sales of fluted pumpkin vines and pods. From the analysis, net returns, benefit to cost ratio, return on investment and shepherd future were deduced and presented in Tables 2a and 2b.

Table 2a: Results of Costs and Returns Analysis of Wet Season Smallholder Fluted Pumpkin Production (n=60)

Inputs Used	Quantity	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost (₦)
Variable Inputs			
Labour (Mandays)	33	1,500	49500
Seed (Pods)	27	1,120	30,240
Fertilizer (Kg)	22.3	500	11,150
Poultry manure (bag)	5	600	3,000
Pesticides (litres)	2	3500	7,000
Stakes (stands)	36	150	5,400
Transportation	-	-	9000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			115,290
Fixed Inputs			
Land (Hectares)	0.5417	50,000	27,085
Hoes	1	1,500	1,500
Cutlasses	2	500	1,000
Baskets	3	500	1500
Bags	5	300	1500
Harvesting knife	2	500	1000
Total Fixed Cost (TFC)			33,585
Total Cost (TC) = TVC + TFC			148,875
Revenue From;			
Fluted Pumpkin Vines (Kg)	1,508.3	150	226,245
Fluted Pumpkin Pods (Pods)	48	1,120	53,760
Total Revenue (TR)			280,005
Net Return (NR) = TR – TC			131,130
Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) = TR/TC			1.88
Return on Investment (ROI) = NR/TC			0.88
Shepherd Future (SF) = (TC/TR)100			53.2%

Source: Field Computation, 2021

**Table: 2b Results of Costs and Returns Analysis of Dry Season Smallholder
Fluted Pumpkin Production**

Inputs Used	Quantity	Unit Cost (₦)	Total Cost (₦)
Variable Inputs			
Labour (Mandays)	32	1,500	48000
Seed (Pods)	21	1,120	23,520
Fertilizer (Kg)	15	500	7500
Poultry manure (bag)	5	600	3,000
Pesticides (litres)	2	3500	7,000
Water (gallon)	2500	10	25000
Stakes (stands)	36	150	5,400
Transportation	-	-	9000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)			119,420
Fixed Inputs			
Land (Hectares)	0.5417	50,000	27,085
Hoes	1	1,500	1,500
Cutlasses	2	500	1,000
Watering Can	2	500	2000
Baskets	3	500	1500
Bags	5	300	1500
Harvesting knife	2	500	1000
Total Fixed Cost (TFC)			35,585
Total Cost (TC) = TVC + TFC			155,005
Revenue From;			
Fluted Pumpkin Vines (Kg)	1007.8	300	302,340
Fluted Pumpkin Pods (Pods)	18	2000	36,000
Total Revenue (TR)			338,340
Net Return (NR) = TR – TC			183,335
Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) = TR/TC			2.18
Return on Investment (ROI) = NR/TC			1.18
Shepherd Future (SF) = (TC/TR)100			45.8%

Source: Field Computation, 2021

From Tables 2a and 2b, the total costs and total revenues of smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in wet and dry season production in the study area were ₦148,875 and ₦280,005; ₦155,005 and ₦338,340 respectively. Net return of ₦131,130 and ₦183,335 for wet and dry season production respectively. Benefit to cost ratios were 1.88 and 2.18 respectively and returns on investment were 0.88 and 1.18, with shepherd future of 53.2% and 45.8% for wet and dry season

production of fluted pumpkin respectively. The benefit-cost ratios of 1.88 and 2.18 showed that every ₦1 invested on fluted pumpkin, returns on investment were 88k and ₦1.18 respectively. These results implied that wet season and dry season smallholder fluted pumpkin production in the area were profitable and shepherd future of 53.2% and 45.8% showed that future of fluted pumpkin investors in the area is bright in all the seasons. These findings agreed with Ayinde, Akerele, and Ojениyi (2007); Idowu, Alimi, Tijani and Okobi (2007) who reported fluted pumpkin production as being profitable under existing production systems with an average net income of \$205.90/ha. The findings were also in consonance with Ogisi, Chukwuji and Okeke (2014) who reported benefit-cost ratio of \$1 to \$1.23 which implied that for every \$1 invested, 23cents was realized and concluded that, fluted pumpkin production was profitable. The findings were also in line with Olowa and Olowa (2016) whose work reported net profit of ₦380,150 and ₦207,150; Shepherd-future of 36.6% and 28.5%; benefit-cost ratios 2.7 and 3.5 for fluted pumpkin farming during rainy season and dry season respectively. They maintained that the results of benefit-cost ratios indicated that fluted pumpkin farming during dry season yielded greater revenue in excess of operational and overhead costs when compared to rainy season farming. Similarly, the shepherd-future indicated greater economic efficiency in the production of fluted pumpkin farming during dry season relative to rainy season. Intensive fluted pumpkin farming during dry season therefore guarantees higher income among small scale fluted pumpkin farmers. This result disagreed with similar studies in literature (Gani and Omonona, 2009; Ayoola, 2014; Olowa and Olowa, 2016) and maintained that, farmers should not invest in irrigation for fluted pumpkin production and that, increased access to land, fertilizers and improved seeds would promote profitability and commercialization of fluted pumpkin enterprises in

Nigeria. Akanni-John, Shaib-Rahim, Eniola, and Elesho (2020) also agreed with the findings of this work that fluted pumpkin production was a profitable venture with over 40% shepherd future. Nwauwa and Omonona (2010) maintained that fluted pumpkin production under irrigation system was more profitable compared to rain-fed system, thus agreeing with the findings of this work. The findings were also in consonance with Adebisi-Adelani, Olajide-Taiwo, Adeoye, Olajide-Taiwo (2011) who generally maintained that fluted pumpkin is the most important and extensively cultivated food and income generating crops in many parts of Africa.

Sources of Water for Dry Season Production of Fluted Pumpkin in the Area

Irrigation has been used to increase production levels in many nations and is used for the production of a whole range of crops including vegetables. Increased crop production depends largely on rainfall reliability. However, rainfall patterns in Nigeria are erratic in distribution, which affects crop production directly. Sources of water for dry season production of fluted pumpkin were identified according to the farmers' responses and presented in table 4

Table 3: Sources of water for Dry Season Production of Fluted Pumpkin in the Study Area (n=60)

Sources of Water	Frequency	Percentage
Bore-holes	5	8.3
Stream	33	55
Pond	2	3.3
River	1	1.7
Well (Dug-outs)	3	5
Wastewater	16	26.7
Modern Irrigation System	0	0
Total	60	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 3, the result of sources of water identified and analyzed showed that majority (55%) of the smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers use stream water for dry season vegetable production. From investigation, in the study area, there is a popular perennial and spiritual stream called “Ibii” that has never dried in the dry season. The farmers within the axis enjoy mass production of fluted pumpkin and other vegetables during the dry season using the source of water. This finding agreed with Obuobie (2003) who maintained that source of water or its quality is of little concern to farmers but what is important to them is its uninterrupted availability and that they do not have to pay for it. Other sources of water used in dry season production of fluted pumpkin were wastewater (26.7%), bore-hole (8.3%), well or dug-outs (5%), pond (3.3%), and river (1.7%) of the respondents respectively. Another significant proportion of irrigation water in the study area is wastewater. This finding agreed with Hussain *et al* (2001) report on estimates that at least 20 million hectares in 50 countries are irrigated with raw or partially treated wastewater. And also, Smith and Nasr (1992) who estimated that one-tenth or more of the world’s population consumes foods produced on land irrigated with wastewater. This finding disagreed with Buechler (2004) who observed that in hot climates with long dry season, high rates of evaporation cause wastewater to be more saline with high total dissolved solids concentration which may restrict the variety of crops that can be cultivated. Some percentages of the farmers patronize bore-hole owners at ₦10 per 25litres gallon, hence the researcher’s standard for measuring water quantity and average cost in the study area.

Constraints on Profitable Fluted Pumpkin Production in the Study Area

The constraints on profitable fluted pumpkin production in the study area were identified, analyzed and classified under production, economic and managerial constraints and presented in Table 4. A factor was considered a

constraint on profitable fluted pumpkin production if loaded at least up to 0.400 in relation to the Kaiser's rule of thumb of ≥ 0.4 .

Table 4: Principal Component Analysis of Constraints on Profitable Fluted Pumpkin Production in the Study Area (n=60)

S/N	Constraints	Production	Economic	Managerial
1.	Inadequate improved varieties of seed	0.518	-0.216	0.0125
2.	High cost of inputs	-0.0925	0.526	0.0715
3.	Inadequate extension contact	0.036	0.0935	0.5885
4.	Nature of land ownership	0.043	0.052	0.526
5.	Pests and diseases	0.455	0.0145	0.194
6.	Instability of product prices	0.123	0.4655	-0.0128
7.	Poor market information	0.1332	-0.218	0.563
8.	Poor feeder road	0.581	0.0385	0.042
9.	High cost of transportation	0.152	0.4635	0.1255
10.	Poor implementation of Government policies	0.4375	-0.107	0.0325
11.	Lack of irrigation facilities	0.346	0.1362	0.518
12.	Inadequate credit facilities	0.214	0.5331	0.063
13.	Poor storage facilities	-0.192	0.2445	0.4065
14.	Lack of processing facilities	0.0698	0.349	0.5162

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 5, the factors that were classified as production constraints were inadequate improved varieties of seeds (0.518), pests and diseases (0.455), poor feeder roads (0.581) and poor implementation of government policies (0.4375). Also the economic constraints were high cost of inputs (0.526), instability of product prices (0.4655), high cost of transportation (0.4635) and inadequate credit facilities (0.5331). Furthermore, the managerial constraints were inadequate extension contact (0.5885), nature of land ownership (0.526), poor market information (0.563), Lack of irrigation facilities (0.518), poor storage facilities (0.4065) and lack of processing facilities (0.5162). These findings were in line with the findings of Nwibo and Okories (2013), who used same procedure to isolate and

categorise agricultural constraints into production, economic and managerial and maintained that these constraints hinder production processes in their different categories. These findings agreed with Nwosu, Onyeneke and Okoli, (2012) whose work reported lack of credit facilities, lack of availability of inputs, pests and disease infestation, inadequate information about input and output prices, and poor road network respectively as constraints on profitable fluted pumpkin production. This was consistent with Onyebinama (2004) who reported that farm input markets face several constraints which range from accessibility and affordability of inputs owing to its high prices, though governments subsidizes the farm input but it always arrives very late and therefore leaves farmers at the mercy of open market traders. Nwachukwu (2008) reported that one of the major constraints facing smallholder farmers were lack of fund to actually plan and execute their agricultural undertakings. This result agreed also, with Swindell (2005) who reported that the produce of farmers face the problem of price fluctuations, as such produce are not sold at prices that would cover cost of production let alone leaving surplus to cover or pay for the efforts of the farmers. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Karunwi and Ezumah (1988) who identified the major constraints to increase production and processing as high cost of transportation, lack of capital and market uncertainty and the tedious operations of processing. The result of poor extension contact concurs to the finding of Unammah (2003) who reported that poor ratio of extension agent to farmers in most developing countries resulted in farmers not having access to improved technologies. Regarding nature of land ownership, this finding is consistent with findings of Spencer (2002) who stated that smallholder farmers in Nigeria have remained subsistent oriented due to inadequacy of resources as well as the system of land ownership, thus, need assistance to rise beyond subsistence level. The results

agreed with Mustapha *et al.* (2016), FAO (2006) who reported pest and diseases, inadequate credit facilities and high interest rate, perishability of produce, water shortage and lack of ready market as major constraints on profitability of vegetable production. Okpeke and Adaigho (2016) agreed with this finding as they reported lack of access to credit facilities, high cost of transportation, lack of storage facilities, and scarcity of viable seeds as major constraints, thus classifying seasonality in production, problem of land acquisition, price fluctuation, and pest and disease infestation as minor constraints in disagreement to this finding. Ogisi, *et al.* (2014) agreed with this finding that unpredictable market, high cost of labour, problem of storage and land acquisition, seed scarcity, lack of equipment and high cost of transportation were serious constraint to fluted pumpkin production. Goni, *et al.* (2013) generally agreed with the findings of this work that rain-fed agriculture is the most common practice in Nigeria as more than three quarters of the country's agricultural area is rain-fed and subsistence in nature and maintained that, rain-fed agriculture can no longer cope with the increasing food demand throughout the year as a result of growing population coupled with climate change. This made rain fed agriculture unreliable as well as unpredictable and therefore has to be supplemented with irrigation for effective agricultural production to be realized.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the smallholder fluted pumpkin farmers in the area were still young and were majorly married females with sizeable households, had secondary education with few years of farming experience, small land holdings and majorly none member of cooperatives, with low frequency of extension contact and meagre annual farm income. The benefit-cost ratios of 1.88 and 2.18 showed that every ₦1 invested on fluted pumpkin production, return on

investment were 88k and ₦1.18 respectively implied that wet and dry season smallholder fluted pumpkin production in the area were profitable and shepherd future of 53.2% and 45.8% respectively implied high economic efficiency for wet and dry season smallholder fluted pumpkin production in the study area.

Recommendations

Based on the major findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1) To obtain farm resource inputs and other farm implements at subsidised rate from the government and non-governmental organisation, farmers are advised to join cooperative societies.

2) Extension agents in the area should be encouraged by providing favourable conditions of service to promote quality extension service delivery

3) All season production of fluted pumpkin should be through modern irrigation facilities.

4) Modern storage and processing facilities should be provided to reduce deterioration and postharvest losses of the produce.

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